

Investigations on the Solvolysis of Molybdenyl(V) Cation in Acetylacetone

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Pyridinium oxotrihalo-acetylacetonato molybdate(V), $\text{PyH}[\text{MoOX}_3\text{.acac}]$, has been isolated in the pure state by refluxing pyridinium oxopentahalomolybdate(V), $(\text{PyH})_3[\text{MoOCl}_5]$ with acetylacetone. However, refluxing bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline salts of oxohalomolybdate(V) with acetylacetone results in *trans*-oxotrihalo(L)-molybdenum(V) $[\text{MoOX}_3\text{.L}]$ ($X = \text{Cl, Br}$ and $L = \text{bipy}$ or *phen*). Non-electrolytic oxodihalo(pyridine)(acetylacetonato)molybdenum(V) $[\text{MoOX}_2\text{.acac.Py}]$ (*acac* = acetylacetone) has been synthesised by thermal dehydrohalogenation of $\text{PyH}[\text{MoOX}_3\text{.acac}]$. All these are the manifestation of the solvolytic reaction of molybdenyl(V) cation " MoO^{3+} " with acetyl acetone. All the compounds have been studied by various physicochemical methods.

EARLIER reports¹⁻³ from this laboratory established that the mode of dehydrohalogenation reaction of oxohalomolybdate(V) of organic bases in solution largely depends on the basicity of the ligand associated with the salt as well as on the ability of the solvent to interact with the compound. In order to take up a comparative study, we were interested in investigating the reactions of two types of oxohalomolybdates(V), [(i) with pyridinium cation containing single potential hetero nitrogen atom and (ii) with bipyridinium cation having double potential nitrogen atoms e.g., 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline] with a β -diketone e.g., acetylacetone. The reactions were carried out according to the following scheme :

($X = \text{Cl, Br}$; $L = 2,2'$ -bipyridyl or 1,10-phenanthroline)

It is interesting to note that in reaction 1 acetyl acetone acts as a coordinating ligand to the oxometal entity MoO^{3+} under the direct influence of the strongly basic pyridine, thereby preventing the reactant to undergo elimination of two molecules of hydrogen halide to yield the expected non-electrolyte. In reaction 2, however, in contrast to reaction 1, it simply acts as a dehydrohalogenating solvent to drive off two molecules of hydrogen halide under the influence of the more potential ligand, 2,2'-bipyridyl or 1,10-phenanthroline. To synthesise the interesting non-electrolytic acetylacetonato complexes, an indirect method was adopted by heating the pyridinium oxotrihalo-acetylacetonato molybdate(V),

$\text{PyH}[\text{MoOX}_3\text{.acac}]$ (*acac* = acetylacetone), slowly in solid state. The products were paramagnetic solids of composition $[\text{MoOX}_2(\text{acac})(\text{Py})]$, a coordinate system with a Cs symmetry.

No such product could be obtained in the case of oxohalomolybdates of α -picoline, piperidine, alkali metal ions, ammonium, ethylene diamine, etc. It is thus evident that the reactions of the molybdenyl cation MoO^{3+} in $\text{RH}_3[\text{MoOX}_5]$ with acetylacetone are functions of the base 'R' of the oxohalomolybdates. All the oxohalomolybdates were synthesised by the novel method described earlier by Saha and co-workers^{4,5}. The stereochemical configuration of the non-electrolyte $\text{MoOX}_3\text{.L}$ ($L = 2,2'$ -bipyridyl or 1,10-phenanthroline) has been adjudged simply by studying its chemical inertness towards hydrolysis leading to the production of oxobridge compounds.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A. R. grade. The salts $\text{RH}_3[\text{MoOX}_5]$ were prepared by standard methods^{4,5}.

Analysis : Molybdenum^{4,5} and halogens were estimated gravimetrically as MoO_3 , AgCl and AgBr , respectively. Nitrogen was estimated by Dumas' method. Oxidation state of the metal was determined by ceric sulphate method.

Pyridinium oxotrichloro-acetylacetonato molybdate(V), $\text{PyH}[\text{MoOX}_3\text{.acac}]$: Pyridinium oxopentachloro/bromomolybdate(V) $(\text{PyH})_3[\text{MoOX}_5]$ ($X = \text{Cl, Br}$) (~ 1.0 g) was boiled under reflux with acetylacetone (15 ml) for 15-20 min. The mixtures were then concentrated and cooled slowly to room

temperature when a brown crystalline chloro derivative or a shining chocolate brown bromo derivative was obtained. These were dried in a vacuum desiccator over solid KOH. Yield was about 0.6 g in case of the chloro derivative and 0.56 g for the bromo derivative. Found : Mo, 23.97; Cl, 26.35; N, 3.40. Calcd. for $\text{PyH}[\text{MoOCl}_3.\text{acac}]$ i.e., $(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N})[\text{MoOCl}_3.\text{acac}]$; Mo, 24.09; Cl, 26.72; N, 3.57%. Found : Mo, 17.98; Br, 45.02; N, 2.47. Calcd. for $\text{PyH}[\text{MoOBr}_3.\text{acac}]$; Mo, 18.04; Br, 45.11; N, 2.63%. Oxidation state of the metal was found to be around 5.1.

Oxodihalo (pyridine) (acetylacetonato) molybdenum(V) $[\text{MoOX}_3.\text{acac}(\text{Py})]$: Samples of $\text{PyH}[\text{MoOX}_3.\text{acac}]$ (~1.0 g), prepared by the method described above, were heated at 100° in a metal block furnace in an inert atmosphere till the evolution of hydrogen halide ceased. Bluish-black chloro derivative and greyish green bromo compounds were recovered. These were obtained in good yields. Found : Mo, 26.25; Cl, 19.68; N, 4.11. Calcd. for $[\text{MoOCl}_3.\text{acac}(\text{Py})]$; Mo, 26.58; Cl, 19.67; N, 3.88%. Found : Mo, 21.12; Br, 35.20; N, 2.79. Calcd. for $[\text{MoOBr}_3.\text{acac}(\text{Py})]$; Mo, 21.27; Br, 25.47; N, 3.10%. Oxidation state of the metal was found to be around 4.9.

Trans-oxotrihalo(L) molybdenum(V) $[\text{MoOX}_3.\text{L}]$ (L=bipy, phen; X=Cl, Br): Samples of the oxohalomolybdates (~1.0 g) of organic bases prepared by previous methods^{4,5} were refluxed with acetylacetone (15 ml) till the elimination of hydrogen halide ceased. Bright green *trans*-bipy-chloro and phen-chloro compounds and chocolate *trans*-bipy-bromo and phen-bromo compounds were isolated. These were filtered and dried in a vacuum desiccator over solid KOH. Yields in all the cases were > 85%. Found : Mo, 25.20; Cl, 28.61; N, 6.72. Calcd. for *trans*- $[\text{MoOCl}_3.\text{bipy}]$; Mo, 25.65; Cl, 28.47; N, 7.08%. Found : Mo, 24.17; Cl, 26.56; N, 6.99. Calcd. for *trans*- $[\text{MoOCl}_3.\text{phen}]$; Mo, 24.07; Cl, 26.73; N, 7.03%. Found : Mo, 18.72; Br, 47.07; N, 5.38. Calcd. for *trans*- $[\text{MoOBr}_3.\text{bipy}]$; Mo, 18.88; Br, 47.24; N, 5.51%. Found : Mo, 18.35; Br, 45.55; N, 4.95. Calcd. for *trans*- $[\text{MoOBr}_3.\text{phen}]$; Mo, 18.03; Br, 45.11; N, 5.26%. The chemical inertness of these compounds towards hydrolysis suggests their *trans* configuration.

Conductance: Molar conductances of the salts $\text{PyH}[\text{MoOX}_3.\text{acac}]$ and non-electrolytes $[\text{MoOX}_3.\text{acac}.\text{Py}]$ were found out in 10^{-3} M solution both in distilled nitrobenzene and acetonitrile media. The values were 135, 135, 56 and 83 $\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2$ in acetonitrile for the salts $\text{PyH}[\text{MoOCl}_3.\text{acac}]$ and $\text{PyH}[\text{MoOBr}_3.\text{acac}]$ and for non-electrolytes $[\text{MoOCl}_3.\text{acac}(\text{Py})]$ and $[\text{MoOBr}_3.\text{acac}(\text{Py})]$, respectively. These values in nitrobenzene were 21, 23, 4 and 4 $\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2$, respectively.

In case of the salts $\text{PyH}[\text{MoOX}_3.\text{acac}]$, the molar conductivities in acetonitrile and nitrobenzene were 135 and 21-23, respectively. These clearly show that the salts are 1:1 electrolytes⁶. Molar conducti-

vities of $[\text{MoOX}_3.\text{acac}(\text{Py})]$ are 56-83 in acetonitrile and 4 in nitrobenzene which indicate their non-electrolytic character as is expected from the proposed molecular formula.

Magnetic susceptibility: Magnetic susceptibilities were measured in a Gouy balance at room temperature using a field strength of 8500 G and the values of the magnetic moments in Bohr Magnetons were determined using the formula $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.839 (X'_M \cdot T)^{\frac{1}{2}}$, where X'_M is the corrected molar susceptibility. The values of the paramagnetic moments μ_{eff} for $\text{PyH}[\text{MoOCl}_3.\text{acac}]$, $[\text{MoOCl}_3.\text{acac}(\text{Py})]$, $[\text{MoOBr}_3.\text{acac}(\text{Py})]$, *trans*- $[\text{MoOCl}_3.\text{bipy}]$, *trans*- $[\text{MoOCl}_3.\text{phen}]$, *trans*- $[\text{MoOBr}_3.\text{bipy}]$ and *trans*- $[\text{MoOBr}_3.\text{phen}]$ were 1.30, 2.04, 1.68, 1.82, 1.75, 1.60 and 1.81 B.M., respectively at room temperature. The results are in good agreement with the d^1 configuration of the quinquevalent molybdenum.

IR spectra: IR spectra of the compounds, recorded in Perkin-Elmer IR spectrophotometer in KBr pellets, show that all of them possess absorption bands in the region 960-985 cm^{-1} (Table 1), characteristic of Mo(V)=O stretching as found in cases of oxohalomolybdenum(V) compounds⁸.

TABLE 1—IR BANDS IN cm^{-1}

Compounds	Main Bands
$(\text{PyH})[\text{MoOCl}_3.\text{acac}]$	750 mb, 890 w, 980 vs, 1160 vw, 1200 vw, 1275 vw, 1340 w, 1475 w, 1520 w, 3000 w,b.
$(\text{PyH})[\text{MoOBr}_3.\text{acac}]$	730 m,b, 810 vw, 880 vw, 960 vs, 1160 vw, 1200 vw, 1275 vw, 1340 w, 1475 w, 1520 w, 3000 w,b.
$[\text{MoOCl}_3.\text{acac}(\text{Py})]$	750 m,b, 880 m, 965 s, 1050 vw, 1160 vw, 1190 vw, 1230 vw, 1475 w, 1520 w, 1590 w, 3000 w,b.
$[\text{MoOBr}_3.\text{acac}(\text{Py})]$	745 m,b, 910 m, 985 s, 1050 vs, 1160 vw, 1190 vw, 1230 vw, 1475 w, 1520 w, 1590 w, 3000 w,b.

w = weak; s = strong; m = medium; b = broad; vs = very strong; vw = very weak.

Electronic spectra: UV and visible spectra of the compounds were recorded in Hilger Uvispek in acetonitrile medium. It is interesting to note that the spectral characteristics^{7,8} of the salts $\text{PyH}[\text{MoOX}_3.\text{acac}]$ and its non-electrolytic derivatives $[\text{MoOX}_3.\text{acac}.\text{Py}]$ are very much identical. The first transition due to $d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{xz}$, d_{yz} appears around 14,000 cm^{-1} and the second one due to $d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{xy}$ appears in the region 20,000-21,000 cm^{-1} . The third band in the region 22,000-24,000 cm^{-1} may be assigned to the $\pi_g \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ transition, whereas the intraligand (β -diketone) transition $\pi_g \rightarrow \pi_g$ appears in the region 25,000-27,000 cm^{-1} . The bands along with their molar extinction coefficients and the probable assignments are tabulated in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Compounds	λ_{\max} (μm)	$(\text{cm}^{-1} \times 10^{-3})$	ϵ	Possible assignments
(PyH)[MoOCl ₃ .acac]	710	14	12.85	$d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow (d_{xz}, d_{yz})$
	470	21.3	49.42	$d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{xy}$
	420	23.8	85.15	$\pi_g \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$
	370	27.0	247.1	$\pi_g \rightarrow \pi_4$
(PyH)[MoOBr ₃ .acac]	710	14	28.81	$d_{x^2-y^2} (d_{xz}, d_{yz})$
	482	20.75	464.8	$d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{xy}$
	415	24.10	1706	$\pi_g \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$
	382	26.17	1826	$\pi_g \rightarrow \pi_4$
[MoOCl ₃ .acac.(Py)]	710	14	82.00	$d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow (d_{xz}, d_{yz})$
	488	20.49	29.84	$d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{xy}$
	435	22.99	70.66	$\pi_g \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$
	370	27.0	309.8	$\pi_g \rightarrow \pi_4$
[MoOBr ₃ .acac.(Py)]	710	14	116.3	$d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow (d_{xz}, d_{yz})$
	475	21.05	325.5	$d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{xy}$
	415	24.10	2164.0	$\pi_g \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$
	385	26.97	2527.0	$\pi_g \rightarrow \pi_4$

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